

Ultrametric Lindenmayer systems over prime alphabets: p -adic fractals and boundary dynamics

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Abstract

Parallel rewriting in the sense of Lindenmayer generates branching patterns whose prefix trees carry a natural ultrametric. For a prime p , we introduce *ultrametric Lindenmayer systems of prime type p* (UL_pS) by identifying the p -ary prefix tree with the tree of basic balls in \mathbf{Z}_p and by taking labeled local refinement rules as the primary data. Every UL_pS canonically determines a graph-directed iterated function system on \mathbf{Z}_p , and its limit set $\Lambda(S)$ is a p -adic path set fractal. The disjointness of the cosets $d + p\mathbf{Z}_p$ makes the open set condition automatic; under irreducibility and non-emptiness,

$$\dim_H \Lambda(S) = \frac{\log \rho(M_{\text{acc}})}{\log p}.$$

The transition graph also yields grammar-level criteria for non-emptiness, surjectivity, perfection, and reducibility.

We further study constant-length substitutions $\sigma : \Sigma_p \rightarrow \Sigma_p^k$ through the induced boundary maps $F_\sigma : \mathbf{Z}_p \rightarrow \mathbf{Z}_p$. These maps satisfy a k -power Hölder law, with equality for all distinct points precisely in the prefix-injective case, and their images have Hausdorff dimension $\log m / (k \log p)$, where m is the number of distinct substituted blocks. Examples include Fibonacci-type grammars, Thue–Morse, a 3-adic Cantor set, and a schematic coral rule.

Keywords: ultrametric Lindenmayer system, p -adic integers, path set fractal, constant-length substitution, Hausdorff dimension, graph-directed iterated function system

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1. Introduction

Lindenmayer systems generate branching patterns from parallel local rules, yet the prefix hierarchy of a derivation carries a natural ultrametric structure that the standard Euclidean embedding [1] discards: two developments are close when they share a long common initial segment, regardless of where their tips land in \mathbf{R}^n . The foundational sources [1–3] span biology-oriented modeling, formal language theory, and algorithmic visualization; complementary to those classical viewpoints, the prefix tree itself carries an intrinsic geometric structure, which we develop here.

Fix a prime p . The rooted p -ary prefix tree of an L-system over $\Sigma_p = \{0, \dots, p-1\}$ is canonically isomorphic to the tree of basic balls in \mathbf{Z}_p : a finite word corresponds to a ball, extending the word passes to a subball, and a complete infinite development determines a unique p -adic integer. The p -adic metric equips the branching hierarchy with a non-Archimedean analytic structure in which proximity records common ancestry rather than spatial separation. In a companion article [4], this ball hierarchy serves as the spatial substrate for a Vladimirov reaction–diffusion system on \mathbf{Z}_3 modeling coral calcification; the present article develops the mathematical framework. (The ultrametric geometry of prefixes exists for every finite alphabet; we restrict to the prime-digit case, where the alignment with \mathbf{Z}_p is transparent; Remark 3.4 records the general n -adic picture.)

This correspondence leads to *ultrametric Lindenmayer systems of prime type p* (UL $_p$ S), *i.e.* labeled refinement dynamics on the tree of basic p -adic balls. A finite label set \mathcal{L} and a refinement rule ρ assigning to each label a subset $\rho(\ell) \subseteq \Sigma_p \times \mathcal{L}$ govern which children each ball admits and what label each child receives. The set of all complete developments of a UL $_p$ S (Definitions 4.1 and 4.3) determines its *limit set* $\Lambda(S) \subseteq \mathbf{Z}_p$ (Definition 4.6), a compact subset that measures the “reach” of the grammar in the p -adic boundary. The formalism operates at the grammar level: accessibility, terminal behavior, branching, and boundary effects are read from the production data ρ , with the geometric realization in \mathbf{Z}_p as a derived structure (Section 5).

Structurally, a UL $_p$ S connects to p -adic fractal geometry. Abram and Lagarias [5] introduced *path set fractals* in \mathbf{Z}_p with dimension controlled by a finite graph, and developed the symbolic path set language in [6]; Hare

and Vávra [7] developed self-similar IFS on \mathbf{Z}_p under their condition (C). On the substitution side, Narbel [8] studied boundaries of iterated morphisms on free semigroups, Canterini and Siegel [9] constructed prefix-suffix automata for primitive substitutions, and Rowland and Yassawi [10] built profinite automata for p -adic integer sequences arising from constant-length substitutions. The identification of \mathbf{Z}_p with the boundary of the rooted p -ary tree is classical. Anashin [11] characterizes finite automata on \mathbf{Z}_p via van der Put series, and Grigorchuk and Savchuk [12] develop the connection between Mealy automata, automatic sequences, and tree endomorphisms on \mathbf{Z}_p . Related but orthogonal spectral questions for p -adic fractal strings, including tube formulas and Minkowski content, are studied by Lapidus and Hùng [13]. The present work takes a rewriting-first viewpoint, complementary to the IFS-first framework of Hare–Vávra: the primary data are local refinement rules $\rho(\ell)$ attached to labels, with the graph-directed IFS on \mathbf{Z}_p derived from these rules via the word–ball correspondence (Proposition 5.7). The limit set is a path set fractal in the sense of [5, 6]. Hare–Vávra’s IFS satisfying condition (C) form a strict subclass of path set fractals [7]; UL_pS form a parallel subclass produced by symbolic rewriting, and the comparison between these two subclasses is taken up in Section 8. Under the hypotheses of Corollary 5.9 (irreducible, nonempty limit set), the Hausdorff dimension of $\Lambda(S)$ satisfies

$$\dim_H \Lambda(S) = \frac{\log \rho(M_{\text{acc}})}{\log p},$$

where M_{acc} is the transition matrix of the subgraph of G_ρ accessible from the initial label (equivalently, the principal submatrix of Definition 5.6 on those labels); if every label is reachable, $M_{\text{acc}} = M$.

In the present digit-based ultrametric setting, the open set condition required by the Mauldin–Williams theory [14] holds automatically, since distinct digits produce disjoint cosets $d + p\mathbf{Z}_p$.

The main contributions are the following.

1. **Ultrametric Lindenmayer systems.** We introduce UL_pS (Definition 4.1), a grammar-driven framework for labeled parallel rewriting on the p -adic ball tree, together with criteria for compactness, non-emptiness, perfection, and surjectivity of the limit set $\Lambda(S)$.
2. **Path set identification and Hausdorff dimension.** We prove that every UL_pS determines a graph-directed IFS on \mathbf{Z}_p satisfying the open

set condition automatically (Proposition 5.7), and obtain $\dim_H \Lambda(S) = \log \rho(M_{\text{acc}}) / \log p$ (Corollary 5.9).

3. **Boundary dynamics of constant-length substitutions (independent of the UL_pS construction).** For any constant-length substitution $\sigma : \Sigma_p \rightarrow \Sigma_p^k$, the induced map $F_\sigma : \mathbf{Z}_p \rightarrow \mathbf{Z}_p$ satisfies an exact k -power Hölder bound; prefix-injectivity is the metric equality case; and the image dimension is $\dim_H F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_p) = \log m / (k \log p)$ (Theorem 6.1).
4. **Worked examples.** Fibonacci-type grammars, Thue–Morse, a 3-adic Cantor set, a schematic coral grammar, and further instances demonstrate the dimension spectrum and boundary-map dichotomy.

Read together, Corollary 5.9 and Theorem 6.1 are independent coordinates on the p -adic boundary: fractal geometry of grammars for $\Lambda(S)$ on one hand, and Lipschitz dynamics of F_σ on the other.

The article is organized as follows. Section 2 recalls the D0L formalism. Section 3 establishes the word–ball–boundary dictionary with \mathbf{Z}_p . Section 4 introduces UL_pS and defines the limit set $\Lambda(S)$ (Definition 4.6), with Example 4.5 illustrating extremes of refinement immediately after the definitions. Sections 5 and 6 contain the results summarized above. Section 7 works out several examples, and Section 8 discusses open problems and connections to p -adic reaction–diffusion [4].

2. Classical Lindenmayer systems and the latent ultrametric structure

We isolate the structural feature of D0L-systems that survives in the ultrametric reformulation, namely the local, context-free production principle. We recall the simplest deterministic setting.

The Lindenmayer feature retained from D0L is the local, parallel, context-free production principle, recast on the hierarchy of basic balls in \mathbf{Z}_p .

Definition 2.1. A *deterministic context-free Lindenmayer system* (D0L-system) is a triple (Σ, ω, σ) where Σ is a finite alphabet, $\omega \in \Sigma^{<\omega}$ is the axiom, and $\sigma : \Sigma \rightarrow \Sigma^{<\omega}$ is a production rule extended to words by parallel substitution:

$$\sigma(a_1 a_2 \cdots a_n) = \sigma(a_1) \sigma(a_2) \cdots \sigma(a_n).$$

Iterating σ produces the sequence $\omega, \sigma(\omega), \sigma^2(\omega), \dots$

Example 2.2 (Lindenmayer’s alga). The D0L-system $(\{A, B\}, A, \sigma)$ with $\sigma(A) = AB$, $\sigma(B) = A$ was introduced in [2] to model the filamentous alga *Anabaena catenula*. Iteration gives:

$$A, \quad AB, \quad ABA, \quad ABAAB, \quad ABAABABA, \quad \dots$$

The word lengths $1, 2, 3, 5, 8, \dots$ are consecutive Fibonacci numbers. Under the relabeling $A \leftrightarrow 0$, $B \leftrightarrow 1$, the same system becomes the substitution $\sigma(0) = 01$, $\sigma(1) = 0$ over Σ_p (with $p = 2$), which has *non-constant length* ($|\sigma(0)| = 2$, $|\sigma(1)| = 1$). The distinction between constant-length and variable-length productions will be central to the continuity analysis of Section 6. This system will reappear in Example 7.2 as a UL_2S , where its limit set $\Lambda(S) \subset \mathbf{Z}_2$ and Hausdorff dimension $\log \varphi / \log 2$ are computed.

The mathematical content we retain from D0L-systems is the rooted hierarchy of prefixes: the empty word is the root; words of length one form the first level; words of length two form the second; and so on. Two infinite developments are close in the natural branching sense when they share a long initial segment before diverging. Turtle-graphics embeddings [1] place L-system derivations in \mathbf{R}^2 or \mathbf{R}^3 , producing elaborate branching patterns, but the Euclidean metric of such embeddings measures spatial proximity of tips rather than derivational proximity of branches. The ultrametric that the prefix tree carries records hierarchical information without passing through an ambient space. This ultrametric viewpoint is not purely heuristic. In earlier work on word topologies, Pin [15] showed that the p -adic topology on the free monoid detects group-theoretic regularity, and Berstel, Crochemore, and Pin [16] used related ideas in the study of the Thue–Morse word. Section 3 turns this latent prefix ultrametric into the explicit word–ball–boundary dictionary with \mathbf{Z}_p .

3. The word–ball–boundary dictionary

Appendix Appendix A summarizes the p -adic absolute value, the base- p expansion, and the ultrametric properties of balls used throughout this section and the rest of the paper.

Let p be a prime and $\Sigma_p := \{0, 1, \dots, p - 1\}$. Write $\Sigma_p^{<\omega}$ for the set of finite words over Σ_p and Σ_p^ω for the set of infinite words. For words u, v (finite or infinite), let $\text{Pref}(u, v)$ denote the length of their maximal common prefix. The *prefix ultrametric* on Σ_p^ω is $d_{\text{pref}}(\alpha, \beta) = p^{-\text{Pref}(\alpha, \beta)}$ for $\alpha \neq \beta$

and $d_{\text{pref}}(\alpha, \alpha) = 0$; the strong triangle inequality is immediate (see [17, Chapter 2] or [18, §1.1]).

Every $x \in \mathbf{Z}_p$ admits a unique expansion $x = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} a_i p^i$ with $a_i \in \Sigma_p$. For a finite word $w = a_0 a_1 \cdots a_{N-1} \in \Sigma_p^{<\omega}$, set $s(w) := \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} a_i p^i$ and define the *basic ball* $B_w := s(w) + p^{\text{len}(w)} \mathbf{Z}_p$. The p -adic expansion establishes:

- (a) For each N , the map $w \mapsto B_w$ is a bijection from Σ_p^N to the set of basic balls of radius p^{-N} in \mathbf{Z}_p .
- (b) If v extends w then $B_v \subseteq B_w$; if $\text{len}(v) = \text{len}(w)$ and $v \neq w$ then $B_v \cap B_w = \emptyset$.

Proposition 3.1 (Word–ball dictionary). *The rooted tree of finite words over Σ_p , ordered by extension, is canonically isomorphic to the rooted tree of basic balls in \mathbf{Z}_p , ordered by reverse inclusion.*

Proof. By item (a), for each $N \geq 0$ the map $w \mapsto B_w$ is a bijection from Σ_p^N to the set of basic balls of radius p^{-N} in \mathbf{Z}_p . It therefore identifies the vertices at level N of the prefix tree with the vertices at level N of the ball tree.

It remains to check compatibility with the tree order. If v extends w , write $\text{len}(w) = N$ and $\text{len}(v) = M \geq N$. Then $v = w d_N \cdots d_{M-1}$ for some digits $d_j \in \Sigma_p$, hence

$$s(v) = s(w) + p^N c$$

for an integer c . Thus $s(v) \equiv s(w) \pmod{p^N}$, and therefore

$$B_v = s(v) + p^M \mathbf{Z}_p \subseteq s(w) + p^N \mathbf{Z}_p = B_w.$$

Conversely, if $w, w' \in \Sigma_p^N$ with $w \neq w'$, then the base- p expansions of the integers $s(w), s(w') \in \{0, \dots, p^N - 1\}$ are distinct, so $s(w) \not\equiv s(w') \pmod{p^N}$. Hence the cosets $B_w = s(w) + p^N \mathbf{Z}_p$ and $B_{w'} = s(w') + p^N \mathbf{Z}_p$ are disjoint. In particular, two distinct vertices at the same level correspond to two distinct disjoint balls.

Therefore $w \mapsto B_w$ preserves levels and sends extension of words exactly to reverse inclusion of balls. The root ε corresponds to $B_\varepsilon = \mathbf{Z}_p$, and adjoining one digit selects one of the p child subballs. This is precisely an isomorphism of rooted trees. \square

Figure 1 illustrates the dictionary for $p = 2$: extension of words (left tree) corresponds to inclusion of balls (right tree). Given $\alpha = (a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots) \in \Sigma_p^\omega$, each infinite word determines a unique point $x_\alpha := \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} a_i p^i \in \mathbf{Z}_p$, characterized by $\{x_\alpha\} = \bigcap_{N \geq 1} B_{\alpha|N}$.

Figure 1: The word–ball dictionary of Proposition 3.1 for $p = 2$. Extension of words corresponds to inclusion of balls.

Proposition 3.2 (Boundary identification). *The map $\Phi: \Sigma_p^\omega \rightarrow \mathbf{Z}_p$, $\alpha \mapsto x_\alpha$, is an isometry from $(\Sigma_p^\omega, d_{\text{pref}})$ onto $(\mathbf{Z}_p, |\cdot|_p)$.*

Proof. Let $\alpha \neq \beta$ and $N = \text{Pref}(\alpha, \beta)$. Then $x_\alpha - x_\beta = p^N u$ for a unit $u \in \mathbf{Z}_p^\times$, so $|x_\alpha - x_\beta|_p = p^{-N} = d_{\text{pref}}(\alpha, \beta)$. Surjectivity follows from the uniqueness of the p -adic expansion. \square

Remark 3.3. The rooted prefix tree used here (vertices = basic balls of \mathbf{Z}_p , edges = refinement) should not be confused with the *Bruhat–Tits tree* of \mathbf{Q}_p , which has as vertices all balls of arbitrary p -adic radius and carries a richer symmetry structure.

Remark 3.4 (Why primality?). For an alphabet of size $n \geq 2$ the prefix tree and its ultrametric are well defined, and the boundary Σ_n^ω is homeomorphic to $\mathbf{Z}_n := \varprojlim \mathbf{Z}/n^k \mathbf{Z}$. When $n = p^r$ is a prime power, $\mathbf{Z}_n \cong \mathbf{Z}_p$ by block refinement. When n has at least two distinct prime factors the Chinese Remainder Theorem gives $\mathbf{Z}_n \cong \prod_i \mathbf{Z}_{p_i}$; this product carries no single non-Archimedean absolute value, and no single local field plays the role that \mathbf{Q}_p plays in the prime case. The dimension formula of Section 5 extends to any n , but the boundary dynamics of Section 6 and the realizability program of the companion paper depend essentially on working over a single local field.

4. Ultrametric Lindenmayer systems in the prime case

The identifications of Section 3 allow us to recast the Lindenmayer principle (context-free rewriting governed by a finite set of production types) as *labeled refinement of basic balls in \mathbf{Z}_p* .

The classical algebra of Example 2.2 is the guiding prototype: under the relabeling $A \leftrightarrow 0$, $B \leftrightarrow 1$, its production rule $A \rightarrow AB$, $B \rightarrow A$ becomes the UL_2S with

$$\rho(A) = \{(0, A), (1, B)\}, \quad \rho(B) = \{(1, A)\},$$

studied in Example 7.2. We now define the general prime-alphabet version.

Definition 4.1. An *ultrametric Lindenmayer system of prime type p* (UL_pS) consists of:

- i. a finite label set \mathcal{L} with a distinguished initial label $\ell_0 \in \mathcal{L}$;
- ii. for each label $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$, a *refinement rule*

$$\rho(\ell) \subseteq \Sigma_p \times \mathcal{L},$$

specifying which digits $d \in \Sigma_p$ produce admissible children and what label each such child receives, with the condition that the digit projection is *deterministic*: if $(d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell)$ and $(d, \ell'') \in \rho(\ell)$ then $\ell' = \ell''$ (each digit determines at most one child label).

The system runs as follows. The root $B_\emptyset = \mathbf{Z}_p$ carries label ℓ_0 . A vertex B_w with label $\lambda(B_w) = \ell$ admits as children the balls B_{wd} for each $(d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell)$; the child B_{wd} receives label $\lambda(B_{wd}) = \ell'$.

Remark 4.2. Finiteness of \mathcal{L} ensures that the system is finitely presented and that the set of admissible digit sequences forms a sofic shift [19]. The definition is more flexible than a classical D0L-system: vertices may branch fully, partially, or not at all (terminal balls).

Definition 4.3. A *development* in a UL_pS is a descending chain

$$B_0 \supseteq B_1 \supseteq B_2 \supseteq \cdots$$

such that B_{n+1} is a child of B_n . A development is *complete* if it is infinite; it is *terminal* if it halts at a ball with $\rho(\lambda(B_n)) = \emptyset$.

By the boundary identification (Proposition 3.2), each complete development determines a unique point $\bigcap_{n \geq 0} B_n = \{x\} \subset \mathbf{Z}_p$. The system therefore generates not only a tree of balls but also a subset of the boundary \mathbf{Z}_p : the set of all limit points of complete developments.

Definition 4.4. Let $S = (\mathcal{L}, \ell_0, \rho)$ be a UL_pS .

- i. S is *full* if for every $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$ and every $d \in \Sigma_p$ there exists ℓ' with $(d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell)$.
- ii. S is *uniform* if $|\rho(\ell)| = k$ for a fixed k independent of ℓ .
- iii. The *transition graph* G_ρ has vertex set \mathcal{L} and a directed edge $\ell \rightarrow \ell'$ whenever $(d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell)$ for some d . The system is *irreducible* if the accessible component of G_ρ from ℓ_0 is strongly connected.

Example 4.5 (Full and terminal binary refinement). Let $p = 2$. Two extreme systems illustrate the range of Definition 4.1.

Full refinement. $\mathcal{L} = \{\ell_0\}$, $\rho(\ell_0) = \{(0, \ell_0), (1, \ell_0)\}$. Every ball splits into both subballs, producing the full rooted binary tree with $\Lambda(S) = \mathbf{Z}_2$.

Terminal pruning. $\mathcal{L} = \{\ell_0, \ell_1\}$, $\rho(\ell_0) = \{(0, \ell_0), (1, \ell_1)\}$, $\rho(\ell_1) = \emptyset$. Balls labeled ℓ_1 admit no continuation, so the only surviving path is $0, 0, 0, \dots$, giving $\Lambda(S) = \{0\}$.

Full refinement yields $\Lambda(S) = \mathbf{Z}_p$ (dimension 1, Figure 2); terminal pruning collapses it to a point. Section 7 develops richer examples with fractional dimension.

Definition 4.6. Let $S = (\mathcal{L}, \ell_0, \rho)$ be a UL_pS . A word $w = a_0 a_1 \cdots a_{N-1}$ in Σ_p^N is *admissible* if there exist labels $\lambda_0, \lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_N$ with $\lambda_0 = \ell_0$ and $(a_i, \lambda_{i+1}) \in \rho(\lambda_i)$ for every $0 \leq i < N$. The *limit set* of S is

$$\Lambda(S) := \left\{ x \in \mathbf{Z}_p : \text{every prefix of the } p\text{-adic expansion of } x \text{ is admissible} \right\}.$$

$$\text{Equivalently, } \Lambda(S) = \bigcap_{N \geq 1} \bigcup_{\substack{w \in \Sigma_p^N \\ w \text{ admissible}}} B_w.$$

Via the isometry Φ , the limit set is identified with the set of infinite paths in the transition graph G_ρ starting at ℓ_0 , projected onto the digit coordinates.

5. Limit sets and Hausdorff dimension

Section 4 defined $\Lambda(S)$ and its admissible words. We establish compactness, criteria for non-emptiness, perfection, and surjectivity, and the Hausdorff dimension formula.

Theorem 5.1 (Compactness). *For every UL_pS , the limit set $\Lambda(S)$ is a compact subset of \mathbf{Z}_p .*

Proof. For each $N \geq 1$, let $A_N = \bigcup_{w \text{ admissible, } |w|=N} B_w$. Each A_N is a finite union of clopen balls, hence closed, and $A_{N+1} \subseteq A_N$ since every admissible word of length $N+1$ has an admissible prefix of length N . Then $\Lambda(S) = \bigcap_{N \geq 1} A_N$ is an intersection of a decreasing sequence of closed subsets of the compact space \mathbf{Z}_p , hence compact. \square

Theorem 5.2 (Non-emptiness). $\Lambda(S) \neq \emptyset$ if and only if the transition graph G_ρ admits an infinite path from ℓ_0 . Equivalently, the accessible component of G_ρ from ℓ_0 contains a cycle.

Proof. If $x \in \Lambda(S)$, its digit expansion provides an infinite admissible sequence and hence an infinite path in G_ρ .

The equivalence between admitting an infinite path from ℓ_0 and having a reachable cycle follows from finiteness of \mathcal{L} : any infinite path $\ell_0, \ell_1, \ell_2, \dots$ in the finite graph G_ρ must repeat some label, say $\ell_i = \ell_j$ with $i < j$; the segment $\ell_i \rightarrow \ell_{i+1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \ell_j = \ell_i$ is a cycle reachable from ℓ_0 . Conversely, if a cycle is reachable, any path entering the cycle can be continued indefinitely, yielding an infinite admissible digit sequence and hence a point of $\Lambda(S)$ via Φ . \square

In applications one needs criteria for when $\Lambda(S)$ is a perfect (hence uncountable) set rather than a finite collection of periodic points. The key quantity is the *digit set* of a label:

$$D(\ell) = \{d \in \Sigma_p : (d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell) \text{ for some } \ell'\}.$$

Proposition 5.3 (Perfection criterion). *Let $S = (\mathcal{L}, \ell_0, \rho)$ be an irreducible $UL_p S$ with $\Lambda(S) \neq \emptyset$.*

- (i) *If $|D(\ell)| = 1$ for every reachable label ℓ , then $\Lambda(S)$ is a singleton $\{x_0\}$, where x_0 is an eventually periodic p -adic integer.*
- (ii) *If $|D(\ell)| \geq 2$ for some reachable label ℓ , then $\Lambda(S)$ is perfect and uncountable.*

Proof. (i) If every reachable label ℓ has $|D(\ell)| = 1$, write $D(\ell) = \{d_\ell\}$. Since the injectivity condition of Definition 4.1 forces $\rho(\ell)$ to contain exactly one pair, at each step i from label ℓ_i the successor label ℓ_{i+1} and digit d_{ℓ_i} are uniquely determined. The label sequence $\ell_0, \ell_1, \ell_2, \dots$ starting from ℓ_0 is therefore uniquely determined. Since \mathcal{L} is finite, this sequence is eventually

periodic, fixing a unique eventually periodic digit sequence $d_{\ell_0}, d_{\ell_1}, \dots$ and hence a unique $x_0 \in \mathbf{Z}_p$. Any $x \in \Lambda(S)$ must follow the same development, so $x = x_0$ and $\Lambda(S) = \{x_0\}$.

(ii) Suppose $|D(\ell^*)| \geq 2$ for some reachable ℓ^* , say $d_1 \neq d_2$ with $(d_i, \ell'_i) \in \rho(\ell^*)$. Fix $x \in \Lambda(S)$ and $N \geq 1$. Let ℓ_N be the label at position N in the development of x , i.e. the label in \mathcal{L} such that $(a_i, \ell_{i+1}) \in \rho(\ell_i)$ for $0 \leq i < N$, where $a_0 a_1 \dots$ is the digit expansion of x . Since the accessible component of G_ρ is strongly connected and both ℓ_N and ℓ^* belong to it, there is a directed path $\ell_N = \lambda_0 \xrightarrow{c_0} \lambda_1 \xrightarrow{c_1} \dots \xrightarrow{c_{m-1}} \lambda_m = \ell^*$ in G_ρ of some length $m \geq 0$. The concatenation $w_{\text{ext}} := a_0 \dots a_{N-1} c_0 \dots c_{m-1}$ is admissible (it follows the label path $\ell_0, \dots, \ell_N, \lambda_1, \dots, \ell^*$). In particular its first N digits agree with those of x , so $w_{\text{ext}} \in \Sigma_p^{N+m}$ and $B_{w_{\text{ext}}} \subseteq B_{x|N}$. Thus one reaches the branching label ℓ^* from the depth- N state along an admissible extension of the prefix of x , using strong connectivity of the accessible component. From ℓ^* , both digits d_1 and d_2 are admissible. Each successor label ℓ'_1, ℓ'_2 lies in the accessible component; since that component is finite and strongly connected, from each of these labels there exists an infinite admissible continuation (for instance by circulating along a directed cycle). This produces two distinct points $y_1, y_2 \in \Lambda(S)$ whose first N digits agree with those of x , so $y_1, y_2 \in B_{x|N}$, while y_1 and y_2 diverge from each other at position $N+m$ (one takes digit d_1 , the other d_2). In particular at least one of y_1, y_2 differs from x , so x is not isolated in $B_{x|N} \cap \Lambda(S)$. Since this holds for every N , x is not isolated in $\Lambda(S)$. As a non-empty closed subset of \mathbf{Z}_p without isolated points, $\Lambda(S)$ is perfect, hence uncountable. \square

Example 5.4 (Alternating system). Take $p = 2$, $\mathcal{L} = \{\ell_0, \ell_1\}$, $\rho(\ell_0) = \{(0, \ell_1)\}$, $\rho(\ell_1) = \{(1, \ell_0)\}$. Every reachable label has $|D(\ell)| = 1$, so Proposition 5.3(i) applies: the unique admissible digit sequence is $0, 1, 0, 1, \dots$, giving $\Lambda(S) = \{-2/3\}$ (since $\sum_{k \geq 0} 4^k = 1/(1-4) = -1/3$ in \mathbf{Z}_2 and the sum equals $2 \cdot (-1/3)$).

Theorem 5.5 (Surjectivity). *Let $S = (\mathcal{L}, \ell_0, \rho)$ be a $UL_p S$. Then $\Lambda(S) = \mathbf{Z}_p$ if and only if for every reachable label ℓ and every digit $d \in \Sigma_p$ there exists ℓ' with $(d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell)$.*

Proof. For the “if” direction: given $x = \sum a_i p^i \in \mathbf{Z}_p$, construct an admissible label sequence inductively. At step i the current label ℓ_i is reachable; the hypothesis provides $(a_i, \ell_{i+1}) \in \rho(\ell_i)$, and ℓ_{i+1} remains reachable. Every prefix of x is therefore admissible, so $x \in \Lambda(S)$.

For the “only if” direction: if some reachable ℓ has no pair $(d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell)$ for a certain digit d , choose any admissible prefix leading to ℓ and append digit d . The resulting ball B_{w-d} contains no point of $\Lambda(S)$, since no admissible path can continue through ℓ with digit d . Hence $\Lambda(S) \neq \mathbf{Z}_p$. \square

The dimension formula rests on the following: each UL_pS yields a graph-directed IFS (GIFS) from the word–ball dictionary, in the sense of Mauldin and Williams [14] (see Hutchinson [20] for the foundational single-graph case and Falconer [21] for a comprehensive treatment).

Definition 5.6. The *transition matrix* of a UL_pS $S = (\mathcal{L}, \ell_0, \rho)$ is the matrix $M \in \mathbf{R}^{\mathcal{L} \times \mathcal{L}}$ defined by

$$M_{\ell, \ell'} = \left| \{d \in \Sigma_p : (d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell)\} \right|.$$

Proposition 5.7 (GIFS structure and path set identification). *Let $S = (\mathcal{L}, \ell_0, \rho)$ be a UL_pS . For each label $\ell \in \mathcal{L}$, write Λ_ℓ for the set of all $x \in \mathbf{Z}_p$ whose digit expansion is the projection of an infinite admissible path in G_ρ starting from ℓ ; in particular $\Lambda(S) = \Lambda_{\ell_0}$.*

- i. *S determines a graph-directed iterated function system on \mathbf{Z}_p with contractions $\varphi_d(x) = d + px$, $d \in \Sigma_p$, each of Lipschitz constant $1/p$. The limit sets satisfy*

$$\Lambda_\ell = \bigcup_{(d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell)} \varphi_d(\Lambda_{\ell'}).$$

- ii. *For distinct digits $d \neq d'$, the images $\varphi_d(\mathbf{Z}_p) = d + p\mathbf{Z}_p$ and $\varphi_{d'}(\mathbf{Z}_p) = d' + p\mathbf{Z}_p$ are disjoint cosets of $p\mathbf{Z}_p$. The open set condition of Mauldin–Williams [14] is therefore satisfied with $U_\ell = \mathbf{Z}_p$ for every ℓ . Since $U_\ell \cap \Lambda_\ell \neq \emptyset$ whenever $\Lambda_\ell \neq \emptyset$, this is in fact the strong open set condition.*
- iii. *An infinite path $\ell_0 \xrightarrow{d_0} \ell_1 \xrightarrow{d_1} \ell_2 \rightarrow \dots$ in G_ρ (where the edge $\ell_i \rightarrow \ell_{i+1}$ carries the digit d_i with $(d_i, \ell_{i+1}) \in \rho(\ell_i)$) projects to the digit sequence (d_0, d_1, \dots) . The admissible digit sequences of S are exactly these projections, so under the isometry Φ the limit set $\Lambda(S)$ is a p -adic path set fractal in the sense of Abram–Lagarias [5].*

Proof. For (i), if $x \in \Lambda_{\ell'}$ and $(d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell)$, the element $\varphi_d(x) = d + px$ has first digit d and its tail is an admissible sequence from ℓ' , so $\varphi_d(x) \in \Lambda_\ell$. Conversely, every $y \in \Lambda_\ell$ has a first digit d and a successor label ℓ' with

$(d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell)$; writing $y = d + px$ gives $x \in \Lambda_{\ell'}$. Part (ii) follows from the ultrametric property: cosets $d + p\mathbf{Z}_p$ for distinct d are pairwise disjoint, so the GIFS pieces are disjoint at each refinement scale. For (iii), a digit sequence (a_0, a_1, \dots) is admissible if and only if there exists a label path $\ell_0 \rightarrow \ell_1 \rightarrow \dots$ with $(a_i, \ell_{i+1}) \in \rho(\ell_i)$ for all i ; this is the defining condition for path set fractals in [5]. \square

Remark 5.8 (Automatic open set condition). Over the reals, verifying the open set condition of Mauldin–Williams is often the main technical obstacle in computing Hausdorff dimension: it typically requires ad hoc geometric arguments or the construction of suitable open sets adapted to the specific IFS (see [14, §3] for examples of the difficulty involved). Proposition 5.7(ii) shows that in the p -adic setting the condition is automatic: disjointness of cosets is a consequence of the ultrametric inequality alone, and no further geometric input is needed beyond the transition matrix.

Once Proposition 5.7 places $\Lambda(S)$ in the GIFS framework, the Mauldin–Williams dimension theorem applies directly.

Corollary 5.9 (Hausdorff dimension). *Let $S = (\mathcal{L}, \ell_0, \rho)$ be an irreducible $UL_p S$ with $\Lambda(S) \neq \emptyset$, and let M be its transition matrix. Let $\mathcal{L}_{\text{acc}} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ be the set of labels reachable from ℓ_0 in G_ρ , and let M_{acc} be the principal submatrix of M indexed by \mathcal{L}_{acc} (the transition matrix of the subgraph induced by \mathcal{L}_{acc}). Since every admissible infinite path from ℓ_0 stays in \mathcal{L}_{acc} , the limit set $\Lambda(S)$ is unchanged if one deletes labels in $\mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{L}_{\text{acc}}$, and under the irreducibility hypothesis the restriction of G_ρ to \mathcal{L}_{acc} is strongly connected. Then*

$$\dim_H \Lambda(S) = \frac{\log \rho(M_{\text{acc}})}{\log p},$$

where $\rho(M_{\text{acc}})$ denotes the spectral radius of M_{acc} . (In particular, if $\mathcal{L}_{\text{acc}} = \mathcal{L}$, this is just $\rho(M)$.)

Proof. By Proposition 5.7, S defines a GIFS satisfying the open set condition with all contractions of ratio $1/p$. The parametric matrix of Mauldin–Williams [14] for the graph-restricted system is $A(s) = p^{-s}M_{\text{acc}}$, with spectral radius $p^{-s}\rho(M_{\text{acc}})$. The equation $\rho(A(s)) = 1$ gives $s = \log \rho(M_{\text{acc}})/\log p$. \square

Remark 5.10 (Reducible systems). When the accessible part of G_ρ from ℓ_0 is not strongly connected, every infinite admissible path eventually enters a

reachable strongly connected component that supports infinite continuations. Consequently, $\Lambda(S)$ is a finite union of affine images of the limit sets of the relevant irreducible sub-systems, one for each possible finite entry path. Hence

$$\dim_H \Lambda(S) = \max_j \dim_H \Lambda_{C_j},$$

where the maximum ranges over the reachable strongly connected components C_j that support infinite admissible paths. The coral grammar (Example 7.7) illustrates the simplest instance: the terminal component $\{T\}$ contributes no infinite development and the dimension is determined by the single non-trivial component $\{G, B\}$.

Remark 5.11 (What the grammatical formalism contributes). Corollary 5.9 follows from the Mauldin–Williams dimension theorem once Proposition 5.7 places $\Lambda(S)$ in the GIFS framework. The contribution of the UL_pS formalism lies upstream: it isolates the combinatorial data of rewriting — labels, accessibility, terminal states, and admissible digit production — as primary objects on the transition graph G_ρ , so that the structural results of Theorems 5.2–5.5 and Remark 5.10 are natural questions about G_ρ and the dimension formula emerges as the output of a grammar-level analysis. The framework canonically produces p -adic path set fractals from rewriting data, and sits naturally alongside the boundary-dynamics theory of Section 6, which is logically independent of the limit-set construction.

Corollary 5.12. *Under the hypotheses of Corollary 5.9, with M_{acc} as there:*

- i. $\dim_H \Lambda(S) = 1$ if and only if $\rho(M_{\text{acc}}) = p$, which holds if and only if S is full on the reachable component (condition Definition 4.4(i) restricted to reachable labels; strictly weaker than global fullness when some labels of \mathcal{L} are unreachable).*
- ii. If S is uniform with $|\rho(\ell)| = k$ for all reachable ℓ , then $\dim_H \Lambda(S) = \log k / \log p$.*

Proof. (i) By the injectivity condition of Definition 4.1, each digit $d \in \Sigma_p$ appears in at most one pair $(d, \ell') \in \rho(\ell)$, so every row sum of M is $|D(\ell)| \leq p$, hence $\rho(M_{\text{acc}}) \leq \|M_{\text{acc}}\|_\infty \leq p$. The matrix M_{acc} is irreducible (strong connectivity on \mathcal{L}_{acc}). If $\rho(M_{\text{acc}}) = p$ but some row of M_{acc} summed to strictly less than p , then $M_{\text{acc}}\mathbf{1} \leq p\mathbf{1}$ with at least one strict inequality; by irreducibility of M_{acc} and the Collatz–Wielandt characterization of the spectral radius, this forces $\rho(M_{\text{acc}}) < p$, a contradiction. Therefore $\rho(M_{\text{acc}}) = p$ if and

only if every row of M_{acc} sums to exactly p , which by the surjectivity criterion of Theorem 5.5 is equivalent to S being full on the reachable component. In that case $\Lambda(S) = \mathbf{Z}_p$ and $\dim_H = 1$.

(ii) Each row of M_{acc} sums to $|\rho(\ell)| = k$ for all $\ell \in \mathcal{L}_{\text{acc}}$, so $M_{\text{acc}}\mathbf{1} = k\mathbf{1}$ and $\rho(M_{\text{acc}}) = k$. \square

Remark 5.13 (Symbolic dynamics). The admissible digit sequences of a UL_pS form the path set determined by the pointed labeled graph (G_ρ, ℓ_0) in the sense of [6]. The associated path set entropy is $\log \rho(M_{\text{acc}})$, so Corollary 5.9 may be read as $\dim_H \Lambda(S) = h_{\text{path}} / \log p$. If one forgets the distinguished initial label, the accessible subgraph also determines a one-sided sofic shift [19] with the same growth rate. The geometric realization in \mathbf{Z}_p adds the automatic open set condition (Proposition 5.7) and the boundary dynamics of Section 6; both rely on the local-field structure of \mathbf{Z}_p .

6. Boundary dynamics of constant-length substitutions

This section develops a second thread of the paper, logically independent of the limit-set theory of Section 5. The object of study is the boundary map $F_\sigma : \mathbf{Z}_p \rightarrow \mathbf{Z}_p$ induced by a constant-length substitution $\sigma : \Sigma_p \rightarrow \Sigma_p^k$. The results below apply to every such substitution; no UL_pS structure is required. Theorem 6.1 gives the contraction laws, injectivity criterion, and Hausdorff dimension of $F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_p)$.

A classical D0L production $\sigma : \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Sigma^*$ typically increases word length; its natural domain of action is the tree of balls rather than the boundary \mathbf{Z}_p . When the production has constant length k ($|\sigma(a)| = k$ for every letter a), each input letter produces exactly k output digits, and the induced boundary map $F_\sigma : \mathbf{Z}_p \rightarrow \mathbf{Z}_p$ is well defined. Spectral properties of constant-length substitutions were first studied by Dekking [22]; Narbel [8] analyzed the boundary of iterated morphisms on free semigroups, and Rowland and Yasawari [10] related certain p -adic integer sequences to profinite automata and to constant-length substitutions on uncountable alphabets. We address the orthogonal question of metric contraction on the p -adic boundary.

Theorem 6.1 (Boundary dynamics of constant-length substitutions). *Let $\sigma : \Sigma_p \rightarrow \Sigma_p^k$ be a substitution of constant length $k \geq 2$, extended to Σ_p^ω by blockwise concatenation: $\sigma(a_0a_1a_2\cdots) = \sigma(a_0)\sigma(a_1)\sigma(a_2)\cdots$. Write $F_\sigma = \Phi \circ \sigma \circ \Phi^{-1} : \mathbf{Z}_p \rightarrow \mathbf{Z}_p$ for the induced boundary map.*

(a) k -power Hölder bound. $|F_\sigma(x) - F_\sigma(y)|_p \leq |x - y|_p^k$ for all $x, y \in \mathbf{Z}_p$.

(b) Exact k -power law. *The following are equivalent:*

- i. σ is prefix-injective: $a \neq b$ implies $\sigma(a)[0] \neq \sigma(b)[0]$;
- ii. equality holds in (a) for every pair $x \neq y$.

(c) Injectivity. F_σ is injective on \mathbf{Z}_p if and only if σ is injective on Σ_p .

(d) Fractal image. Let $m = |\{\sigma(a) : a \in \Sigma_p\}|$ be the number of distinct image words. The image $F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_p)$ is a compact self-similar subset satisfying

$$F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_p) = \bigcup_{a \in \Sigma_p} \left(s(\sigma(a)) + p^k F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_p) \right),$$

which is a union of m distinct pieces (distinct images give distinct residues $s(\sigma(a)) \bmod p^k$, hence disjoint cosets of $p^k \mathbf{Z}_p$). The open set condition is satisfied (disjoint cosets), so the standard self-similar dimension formula in the non-Archimedean setting [7] gives

$$\dim_H F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_p) = \frac{\log m}{k \log p}.$$

When σ is injective, $m = p$ and this equals $1/k$.

Proof. Part (a). Let $N = \text{Pref}(\alpha, \beta)$ where $\alpha = \Phi^{-1}(x)$, $\beta = \Phi^{-1}(y)$. The words share their first N letters and differ at position N . Since σ acts letter by letter, $\sigma(\alpha)$ and $\sigma(\beta)$ share their first kN symbols (the concatenation $\sigma(a_0) \cdots \sigma(a_{N-1})$), so $|F_\sigma(x) - F_\sigma(y)|_p \leq p^{-kN} = |x - y|_p^k$.

Part (b). Under prefix-injectivity, $a_N \neq b_N$ forces $\sigma(a_N)[0] \neq \sigma(b_N)[0]$, so $\text{Pref}(\sigma(\alpha), \sigma(\beta)) = kN$ exactly and the inequality is an equality. Conversely, if $\sigma(a)[0] = \sigma(b)[0]$ for some $a \neq b$, set $x = \Phi(a, 0, 0, \dots)$ and $y = \Phi(b, 0, 0, \dots)$. Then $|x - y|_p = 1$ while $F_\sigma(x)$ and $F_\sigma(y)$ share their first digit, giving $|F_\sigma(x) - F_\sigma(y)|_p \leq p^{-1} < 1 = |x - y|_p^k$.

Part (c). If $\sigma(a) = \sigma(b)$ for $a \neq b$, then $F_\sigma(\Phi(a, \gamma)) = F_\sigma(\Phi(b, \gamma))$ for every $\gamma \in \Sigma_p^\omega$, so F_σ is not injective. Conversely, if σ is injective and $F_\sigma(x) = F_\sigma(y)$, comparing the first block of length k gives $\sigma(a_0) = \sigma(b_0)$, hence $a_0 = b_0$; inductively $a_n = b_n$ for all n , so $x = y$.

Part (d). Every $x \in F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_p)$ has the form $F_\sigma(\Phi(a_0, a_1, \dots))$, whose first k digits are $\sigma(a_0)$, so $x \in s(\sigma(a_0)) + p^k F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_p)$. Conversely, every element of $s(\sigma(a)) + p^k F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_p)$ lies in $F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_p)$, so $F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_p)$ is the attractor of the IFS

$\{x \mapsto s(\sigma(a)) + p^k x\}_{a \in \Sigma_p}$. Distinct words $w \in \Sigma_p^k$ encode distinct integers $s(w) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} w_i p^i \in \{0, \dots, p^k - 1\}$, so the $m = |\{\sigma(a) : a \in \Sigma_p\}|$ distinct image words give m distinct residues $s(\sigma(a)) \bmod p^k$, hence m disjoint cosets of $p^k \mathbf{Z}_p$. The resulting IFS satisfies the open set condition, and the self-similar dimension formula [7, 23] gives $\dim_H = \log m / \log p^k = \log m / (k \log p)$. When σ is injective, $m = p$ and $\dim_H = \log p / (k \log p) = 1/k$. \square

Constant-length substitutions provide the first class in which the boundary dynamics is naturally well-defined; more general productions may require interpreter-type realizations or approximation by dynamics on finite-depth balls.

Question 6.2. Which productions that increase depth by a fixed amount k at each step admit realization by a rational map $f \in \mathbf{Q}_p(x)$ preserving the basic balls of \mathbf{Z}_p ?

By Theorem 6.1, every constant-length substitution yields a 1-Lipschitz self-map of \mathbf{Z}_p . Anashin and Khrennikov [24] characterize the 1-Lipschitz maps on \mathbf{Z}_p as exactly the class of automata functions; the realizability question thus asks when an automaton function arising from a grammatical production extends to a rational map on \mathbf{Q}_p .

7. Examples

The examples are organized to separate the regimes of the preceding theorems. Examples 7.1–7.2 illustrate full versus fractional Hausdorff dimension in the limit set (Corollary 5.9). Examples 7.3–7.6 exhibit the three contraction classes of Theorem 6.1: prefix-injective (exact k -power contraction), injective but not prefix-injective (strict inequality for some pairs), and non-injective (image collapse). Example 7.7 connects the framework to hierarchical growth models, and Example 7.9 shows how the prime p controls dimension for a fixed spectral radius.

Example 7.1 (Selective pruning to a coset). Let $p = 2$, $\mathcal{L} = \{\ell_0, \ell_1\}$, $\rho(\ell_0) = \{(0, \ell_1)\}$, $\rho(\ell_1) = \{(0, \ell_1), (1, \ell_1)\}$. Label ℓ_0 forces digit 0 at the root (transitioning to ℓ_1); from ℓ_1 onward both digits are always admissible, giving $\Lambda_{\ell_1} = \mathbf{Z}_2$. An infinite sequence is admissible from ℓ_0 if and only if its first digit is 0, so

$$\Lambda(S) = \Lambda_{\ell_0} = \varphi_0(\Lambda_{\ell_1}) = 0 + 2\mathbf{Z}_2,$$

a single coset of index 2. Compared with the full and terminal systems of Example 4.5, selective pruning restricts a single level while leaving the rest of the tree intact, yielding a clopen subset of full Hausdorff dimension.

Figure 2: The full binary ball tree in \mathbf{Z}_2 with two levels shown. Every ball splits into both subballs. This is the full-refinement tree from Example 4.5, to be contrasted with the pruned tree of Figure 4.

Example 7.2 (A DOL-system with two labels). Let $p = 2$ and $\mathcal{L} = \{A, B\}$, $\ell_0 = A$. Define

$$\rho(A) = \{(0, A), (1, B)\}, \quad \rho(B) = \{(1, A)\}.$$

A ball labeled A produces two children (digits 0 and 1), labeled A and B respectively. A ball labeled B produces one child (digit 1), labeled A .

The rooted tree generated has the following first two levels:

$$\mathbf{Z}_2 \xrightarrow{A} \{0+2\mathbf{Z}_2 (A), 1+2\mathbf{Z}_2 (B)\} \rightarrow \{0+4\mathbf{Z}_2 (A), 2+4\mathbf{Z}_2 (B), 3+4\mathbf{Z}_2 (A)\}.$$

This example illustrates that the child selection rule depends on the label, not only on the digit, and that branching need not be uniform across the tree.

The transition matrix is $M = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$, whose characteristic polynomial is $\lambda^2 - \lambda - 1$. The spectral radius is the golden ratio $\rho(M) = \varphi = (1 + \sqrt{5})/2$. By Corollary 5.9,

$$\dim_H \Lambda(S) = \frac{\log \varphi}{\log 2} \approx 0.694.$$

The limit set $\Lambda(S) \subsetneq \mathbf{Z}_2$ is a proper compact subset: label B produces only digit 1, so certain digit patterns are forbidden. In the terminology of Section 5, S is irreducible but not full.

The forbidden constraint has a simple description: since $\rho(B) = \{(1, A)\}$, digit 0 is inadmissible from label B , and label B is reached precisely after a digit 1. Consequently the admissible digit sequences are exactly those avoiding the bigram 10 as a consecutive pair. Thus the pointed graph (G_ρ, A) determines a path set whose underlying shift-invariant system is the one-step subshift of finite type defined by forbidding the word 10. The number of admissible words of length N is the Fibonacci number F_{N+2} , consistent with $\rho(M) = \varphi$. Figure 3 shows the resulting fractal pattern through nine levels of refinement (generated by the companion script `ulp_fractal_figures.py`).

Figure 3: The admissible prefix tree of the Fibonacci UL_2S from Example 7.2, shown through nine levels of refinement. The figure complements Figure 4: there the local grammar is visible through labels and missing branches, while here the large-scale fractal pattern is visible. Each root-to-tip path determines a prefix of a 2-adic integer in $\Lambda(S)$, and the overall growth reflects the Fibonacci spectral radius $\rho(M) = \varphi$.

Figure 4: The labeled tree of Example 7.2, with $\mathcal{L} = \{A, B\}$, $\rho(A) = \{(0, A), (1, B)\}$, and $\rho(B) = \{(1, A)\}$. Edge labels are digits, and grammar labels appear below the ball names. Because $\rho(B)$ allows only digit 1, the ball $1 + 2\mathbf{Z}_2$ has the single child $3 + 4\mathbf{Z}_2$; the branch $1 + 4\mathbf{Z}_2$ is absent.

Example 7.3 (The Thue–Morse substitution as a level-doubling development). Consider the DOL-system $(\Sigma_p, 0, \sigma)$ with $p = 2$, where $\sigma(0) = 01$ and $\sigma(1) = 10$. This is the Thue–Morse morphism. Starting from axiom 0, iteration gives:

$$w_0 = 0, \quad w_1 = 01, \quad w_2 = 0110, \quad w_3 = 01101001, \quad \dots$$

Each w_n has length 2^n .

In the ball picture over \mathbf{Z}_2 , each w_n corresponds to the basic ball B_{w_n} of radius 2^{-2^n} :

$$\begin{aligned} B_{w_0} &= 0 + 2\mathbf{Z}_2, \\ B_{w_1} &= 2 + 4\mathbf{Z}_2, & (s(01) = 0 + 1 \cdot 2 = 2) \\ B_{w_2} &= 6 + 16\mathbf{Z}_2, & (s(0110) = 0 + 1 \cdot 2 + 1 \cdot 4 + 0 \cdot 8 = 6) \\ B_{w_3} &= 150 + 256\mathbf{Z}_2. & (s(01101001) = 2 + 4 + 16 + 128 = 150) \end{aligned}$$

One checks directly that these form a strictly descending chain:

$$\mathbf{Z}_2 \supseteq B_{w_0} \supseteq B_{w_1} \supseteq B_{w_2} \supseteq B_{w_3} \supseteq \dots,$$

since σ is prolongable on 0: the image $\sigma(0) = 01$ begins with 0, so $w_{n+1} = \sigma(w_n)$ begins with $\sigma(w_n[0]) = \sigma(0)$, whose first letter is $0 = w_n[0]$; by induction, w_n is a prefix of w_{n+1} for every n .

The sequence (B_{w_n}) therefore forms the substitution analogue of a development (Definition 4.3): a nested chain of basic balls whose intersection consists of a single point,

$$x_{TM} := \Phi(0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, \dots) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} t_i \cdot 2^i \in \mathbf{Z}_2,$$

where $(t_i)_{i \geq 0}$ is the Thue–Morse sequence. This specific element of \mathbf{Z}_2 is the unique point in $\bigcap_{n \geq 0} B_{w_n}$; Figure 5 displays this descending chain.

The induced map $F = \Phi \circ \sigma \circ \Phi^{-1}$ on \mathbf{Z}_2 satisfies $|F(x) - F(y)|_2 = |x - y|_2^2$, a special case of Theorem 6.1(b) with $k = 2$: the Thue–Morse morphism is prefix-injective ($\sigma(0)[0] = 0 \neq 1 = \sigma(1)[0]$), so exact k -power contraction holds.

The fixed point x_{TM} satisfies $F(x_{TM}) = x_{TM}$ and attracts every point of the coset $2\mathbf{Z}_2$ doubly exponentially: since $x_{TM} \in 2\mathbf{Z}_2$, every $x \in 2\mathbf{Z}_2$ satisfies $|x - x_{TM}|_2 \leq 2^{-1}$, hence the exact contraction law yields

$$|F^{on}(x) - x_{TM}|_2 = |x - x_{TM}|_2^{2^n} \rightarrow 0.$$

The complementary fixed point x'_{TM} attracts $1 + 2\mathbf{Z}_2$ by the same law, where $x'_{TM} = \Phi(1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 1, 0, \dots)$.

By Theorem 6.1(d), the image $F(\mathbf{Z}_2)$ satisfies $F(\mathbf{Z}_2) = (2 + 4F(\mathbf{Z}_2)) \cup (1 + 4F(\mathbf{Z}_2))$, since $s(01) = 2$ and $s(10) = 1$. This is a Cantor-like subset of \mathbf{Z}_2 with $\dim_H F(\mathbf{Z}_2) = 1/2$. Altogether: prefix-injectivity \Rightarrow exact 2-power contraction in (b) $\Rightarrow \dim_H F(\mathbf{Z}_2) = \log 2 / (2 \log 2) = 1/2$ from (d) with $(m, k, p) = (2, 2, 2)$. The metric perspective here complements the spectral theory developed by Queffélec [25].

Example 7.4 (A 3-adic Cantor set). Let $p = 3$ and $\mathcal{L} = \{\ell_0\}$, with $\rho(\ell_0) = \{(0, \ell_0), (2, \ell_0)\}$. Digit 1 is forbidden at every level; the admissible digit sequences are exactly those using only digits in $\{0, 2\}$. The system is uniform with $|\rho(\ell_0)| = 2$ and a single label, hence irreducible.

Limit set. By Corollaries 5.9 and 5.12(ii), $\dim_H \Lambda(S) = \log 2 / \log 3 \approx 0.631$. The limit set

$$\Lambda(S) = \left\{ x = \sum_{i \geq 0} a_i 3^i \in \mathbf{Z}_3 : a_i \in \{0, 2\} \text{ for all } i \right\}$$

is the 3-adic counterpart of the classical middle-third Cantor set and a basic example of a p -adic path set fractal in the sense of [5]: where the real

Figure 5: The Thue–Morse development as a descending chain of balls in \mathbf{Z}_2 from Example 7.3. Each ball B_{w_n} has radius 2^{-2^n} , and the chain converges to the 2-adic integer $x_{TM} = \sum_{i \geq 0} t_i 2^i$.

construction removes the open middle third at each stage, the UL_3S forbids the middle digit at each refinement level. Figure 6 displays the admissible residues at depths $N = 1, \dots, 4$; the self-similar pattern is visible as each admissible cell at depth N produces exactly two children at depth $N + 1$.

Boundary dynamics. To illustrate Theorem 6.1 at a prime $p > 2$, define the constant-length substitution $\sigma : \Sigma_3 \rightarrow \Sigma_3^2$ by

$$\sigma(0) = 00, \quad \sigma(1) = 20, \quad \sigma(2) = 22.$$

All three images are distinct, so σ is injective ($m = 3$) and F_σ is injective by Theorem 6.1(c). However, $\sigma(1)[0] = 2 = \sigma(2)[0]$, so σ is *not* prefix-injective: by (b), the inequality in (a) is strict for certain pairs. Concretely, $x = \Phi(1, 0, 0, \dots)$ and $y = \Phi(2, 0, 0, \dots)$ satisfy $|x - y|_3 = 1$ while $|F_\sigma(x) - F_\sigma(y)|_3 \leq 3^{-1} < 1 = |x - y|_3^2$.

By part (d), the image $F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_3)$ satisfies

$$F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_3) = (0 + 9F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_3)) \cup (2 + 9F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_3)) \cup (8 + 9F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_3)),$$

since $s(00) = 0$, $s(20) = 2$, $s(22) = 2 + 2 \cdot 3 = 8$. The three cosets of $9\mathbf{Z}_3$ are disjoint, and $\dim_H F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_3) = \log 3 / (2 \log 3) = 1/2$.

This example cleanly separates the three metric regimes of Theorem 6.1: contrast it with the prefix-injective Thue–Morse (Example 7.3, where equality holds in (a) for all $x \neq y$) and with the non-injective case of Example 7.6 (where $m = 1$ and the image collapses to a point).

Remark 7.5 (Sierpiński embedding). The abstract bijection of Proposition 3.1 can be made concrete in \mathbb{R}^2 for $p = 3$. The classical Sierpiński IFS assigns each digit $d \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ to a vertex v_d of an equilateral triangle and contracts by $1/2$: $x \mapsto (x + v_d)/2$. Each solid sub-triangle at approximation level n corresponds to exactly one ball $a + 3^n\mathbf{Z}_3$: the sub-triangle addressed by the digit string (d_0, \dots, d_{n-1}) corresponds to the ball $\Phi(d_0 \cdots d_{n-1} \cdot \Sigma_p^\omega)$. The UL_3S grammar of Example 7.4 then acts as a *pruning rule*: forbidding digit 1 at every level removes the apex sub-triangle (and all its descendants), leaving only the two base sub-triangles. After infinitely many levels, the surviving set is a Cantor set on the edge $\overline{v_0 v_2}$. Figure 7 illustrates this pruning: panel (a) shows the full Sierpiński triangle (\mathbf{Z}_3 , all three digits active), panel (b) highlights the admissible subset $\Lambda(S)$ (blue) against the background (gray) with digit 1 crossed out, and panel (c) renders $\Lambda(S)$ alone via the chaos-game algorithm.

Figure 6: The 3-adic Cantor set from Example 7.4, shown through the levels $n = 0, \dots, 6$. At each stage the grammar forbids digit 1, leaving 2^n intervals of length 3^{-n} . Each surviving interval represents a 3-adic ball together with its digit address. This iterative view complements the spatial embedding in Figure 7.

Each sub-triangle at level n = one ball $a + 3^n \mathbb{Z}_3$. Digits: 0 = bottom-left, 1 = top, 2 = bottom-right.

Figure 7: The word–ball dictionary of Proposition 3.1 made concrete through the Sierpiński IFS for $p = 3$. Panel (a) shows the full ternary refinement corresponding to \mathbb{Z}_3 . Panel (b) shows the grammar of Example 7.4, which forbids digit 1 at every level. Panel (c) shows the resulting limit set $\Lambda(S)$ alone, rendered by a chaos-game simulation. Its Hausdorff dimension is $\log 2 / \log 3 \approx 0.631$.

Example 7.6 (A non-injective constant-length substitution). Let $p = 2$ and $k = 2$. Define $\sigma(0) = \sigma(1) = 01$. Then σ is constant length but not injective on Σ_p , and not prefix-injective since both letters share the first output digit. Here $m = |\{\sigma(0), \sigma(1)\}| = 1$, so Theorem 6.1(d) gives

$$\dim_H F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_2) = \frac{\log 1}{2 \log 2} = 0.$$

Indeed F_σ is constant: every infinite word maps to the periodic output $010101 \cdots$, so $F_\sigma(\mathbf{Z}_2)$ is a single point.

Example 7.7 (A schematic coral grammar). Let $p = 3$ and $\mathcal{L} = \{G, B, T\}$ (growth, branch, terminal), with $\ell_0 = G$. Define

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(G) &= \{(0, G), (1, B), (2, T)\}, \\ \rho(B) &= \{(0, G), (2, T)\}, \\ \rho(T) &= \emptyset. \end{aligned}$$

A ball labeled G produces all three children: digit 0 continues growth, digit 1 initiates a bifurcation, digit 2 terminates. A ball labeled B bifurcates: one sub-branch (digit 0) reverts to growth, the other (digit 2) terminates; not every branch tip survives. A ball labeled T is terminal: no further refinement occurs. This grammar distills the branching logic of the coral model in [4], where the geometrically relevant structure is hierarchical connectivity rather than spatial position; the full model couples this grammar with a Vladimirov reaction–diffusion equation governing nonlocal diffusion along the branching pathways. For algorithmic visualizations of branching in corals and related marine forms in a classical spatial setting, see [26]. Figure 8 displays the transition graph G_ρ for this grammar: the accessible strongly connected component $\{G, B\}$ and the terminal sink T .

The full system $S = (\{G, B, T\}, G, \rho)$ is not irreducible (T is a sink), but the terminal label T cannot appear in any infinite development since $\rho(T) = \emptyset$. Hence $\Lambda(S) = \Lambda(S')$, where $S' = (\{G, B\}, G, \rho')$ is the pruned system with

$$\rho'(G) = \{(0, G), (1, B)\}, \quad \rho'(B) = \{(0, G)\}.$$

This is the first example in this paper where the accessible label set $\mathcal{L}_{\text{acc}} = \{G, B\}$ is strictly smaller than the full label set $\mathcal{L} = \{G, B, T\}$: the transition

matrix of the original system is the 3×3 matrix

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

with $\rho(M) = \varphi$ (the zero row for T does not affect the dominant eigenvalue), but the accessible submatrix $M_{\text{acc}} = M'$ is the 2×2 Fibonacci matrix below. This illustrates the role of the restriction to \mathcal{L}_{acc} in Corollary 5.9: if one mistakenly used the full 3×3 matrix including T , the spectral radius would be the same (φ), but this is coincidental; for other grammars a sink label can inflate the matrix size without contributing to the spectral radius of the dominant block.

The system S' is irreducible: $G \xrightarrow{1} B$ and $B \xrightarrow{0} G$ make $\{G, B\}$ strongly connected. Its transition matrix is

$$M' = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

the Fibonacci matrix, with $\rho(M') = \varphi$. By Corollary 5.9 applied to S' ,

$$\dim_H \Lambda(S) = \dim_H \Lambda(S') = \frac{\log \varphi}{\log 3} \approx 0.438.$$

The coral grammar occupies a sparser fractal subset of \mathbf{Z}_3 than the D0L-system of Example 7.2 does of \mathbf{Z}_2 : the larger prime spreads the same spectral radius over a coarser hierarchy.

The hierarchical dimension $\log \varphi / \log 3 \approx 0.438$ measures the combinatorial rate at which the grammar diversifies, complementary to Euclidean box-counting dimensions reported for coral outlines ($D \approx 1.1$ – 1.4 , [27]) and 3D reconstructions of marine branching organisms ($D \approx 2.2$ – 2.6 , [28]). In the companion model [4], a Vladimirov reaction–diffusion equation on \mathbf{Z}_p couples this grammatical hierarchy with calcification kinetics, and the present dimension quantifies the combinatorial substrate on which that dynamics acts; restricting the dynamics to $\Lambda(S)$ rather than all of \mathbf{Z}_3 is a natural refinement.

Remark 7.8 (Shared tree topology). The admissible prefix tree of S' has the same topology as the Fibonacci tree (Figure 3), since their accessible

Figure 8: Transition graph G_ρ for the coral grammar of Example 7.7. Edge labels are digits in Σ_3 , and the colors reflect the biological interpretation of the labels. The accessible strongly connected component $\mathcal{L}_{\text{acc}} = \{G, B\}$ determines M_{acc} and hence the Hausdorff dimension, whereas the terminal label T supports no infinite development.

transition matrices coincide: $M_{\text{acc}} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ in both cases. The two grammars therefore have the same underlying branching topology and the same spectral radius, but they are realized in different ambient spaces and with different digit assignments: the Fibonacci example lives in \mathbf{Z}_2 , whereas the coral grammar lives in \mathbf{Z}_3 . Both features affect the resulting limit set, while the spectral radius alone controls only the numerator in the dimension formula. Even for a fixed prime, changing the digit assignment changes the embedded subset while leaving the abstract tree unchanged.

Example 7.9 (The Fibonacci grammar over a pentary tree). Let $p = 5$ and $\mathcal{L} = \{A, B\}$, $\ell_0 = A$, with

$$\rho(A) = \{(0, A), (1, B)\}, \quad \rho(B) = \{(0, A)\}.$$

The productions coincide with those of Example 7.2 (with $p = 2$) and the restricted matrix of Example 7.7 (with $p = 3$): the transition matrix is again $M = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$, with $\rho(M) = \varphi$. The Hausdorff dimension, however, depends on the prime:

$$\dim_H \Lambda(S) = \frac{\log \varphi}{\log 5} \approx 0.299.$$

Collecting the three incarnations:

<i>Prime</i>	<i>Spectral radius</i>	$\dim_H \Lambda(S)$	<i>Example</i>
$p = 2$	φ	$\log \varphi / \log 2 \approx 0.694$	Example 7.2
$p = 3$	φ	$\log \varphi / \log 3 \approx 0.438$	Example 7.7
$p = 5$	φ	$\log \varphi / \log 5 \approx 0.299$	this example

The same spectral radius yields strictly decreasing Hausdorff dimensions as p grows: a wider tree dilutes the same branching rate over more potential children at each node.

Remark 7.10 (Boundary of the framework). Consider the Fibonacci substitution $\sigma(0) = 01$, $\sigma(1) = 0$ over Σ_p with $p = 2$. Its variable length ($|\sigma(0)| = 2$, $|\sigma(1)| = 1$) makes the level function $N \mapsto |\sigma(w)|$ depend on the composition of w , so the natural domain of analysis is the Bratteli–Vershik setting, complementary to the constant-length setting of Theorem 6.1. The UL_pS framework of Section 5 captures Fibonacci-type branching at the level of admissible refinements (Example 7.2).

Remark 7.11 (Computational companion). The accompanying Python scripts reproduce Corollary 5.9 and the figures of Section 7. They are openly archived at Zenodo (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20079326), with source at github.com/yoyontzin/ulp-systems-companion.

- `ulp_dimension.py`: inputs $(p, \mathcal{L}, \ell_0, \rho)$, builds M_{acc} , and prints its spectral radius and $\dim_H \Lambda(S)$ per Corollary 5.9.
- `ulp_fractal_figures.py`: generates Figures 3 and 6.
- `ulp_sierpinski.py`: generates Figure 7.

8. Outlook

We close with several questions left open by the preceding development.

Corollary 5.9 shows that under irreducibility and $\Lambda(S) \neq \emptyset$, each UL_pS yields a p -adic path set fractal with the stated Hausdorff dimension. Which path set fractals arise from Lindenmayer parallel rewriting remains open: each refinement step records both a digit and a child label, which restricts the allowed transition data compared with a completely general path set construction [6], and hence with the broader class of p -adic path set fractals of [5]. These restrictions isolate a subclass of path sets whose precise extent is unknown. The decimation and interleaving operations studied by Abram, Lagarias, and Slonim [29], which preserve the class of path sets, may provide algebraic tools for this classification.

Question 6.2 poses the realizability problem; its automata-theoretic context appears after Theorem 6.1. A companion paper develops approximation methods that lift local ball data to global rational maps on \mathbf{Q}_p .

On the analytic side, the limit set $\Lambda(S)$ is the canonical domain on which to pose a reaction–diffusion equation: it is the compact subset of \mathbf{Z}_p that

the branching grammar actually reaches. The coral model of [4] places a Vladimirov-type PDE on all of \mathbf{Z}_p ; restricting that dynamics to $\Lambda(S)$, where the grammar of growth and the continuous dynamics interact, is a natural next step. A further extension would couple grammatical refinement with the PDE: each new level of branching alters the medium on which the operator acts, and the solution governs which productions fire. Beyond the tree-based model, an important complication is biological anastomosis (fusion of branches), which adds graph connectivity beyond a single ancestral path. Encoding such fusion leads to proximity relations modeled on graphs rather than on one rooted tree alone; how far the present ultrametric toolkit extends under sparse anastomosis is an open direction.

On the measure-theoretic side, the accessible strongly connected part of G_ρ determines a natural one-sided shift of finite type, hence a Parry measure of maximal entropy. Pushing this measure forward through the coding map to $\Lambda(S) \subseteq \mathbf{Z}_p$ yields a natural Borel measure on the p -adic realization, reflecting the maximal-entropy symbolic statistics of the grammar. Fan, Liao, Wang, and Zhou [30] proved that p -adic repellers in \mathbf{Q}_p are subshifts of finite type; exploring the extent to which their dynamical framework interacts with the grammatical structure of UL_pS limit sets is a natural question. Properties of the Parry measure (exact dimensionality, multifractal spectrum) in the p -adic realization are left for future work.

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Appendix A. Primer on p -adic integers

This appendix is addressed to readers unfamiliar with p -adic numbers; those who have worked with \mathbf{Z}_p before may skip it. We collect the definitions and key properties used throughout the paper, emphasizing the features that distinguish the p -adic world from the Euclidean one and make it naturally suited to hierarchical structures. For comprehensive treatments see Gouvêa [17] or Robert [18].

The p -adic absolute value. Let p be a prime. Every nonzero rational $x \in \mathbb{Q}$ can be written uniquely as $x = p^v \cdot a/b$ with $v \in \mathbf{Z}$ and a, b coprime

to p . The p -adic valuation is $v_p(x) := v$, and the p -adic absolute value is

$$|x|_p := p^{-v_p(x)}, \quad |0|_p := 0.$$

This absolute value satisfies the *strong triangle inequality* (ultrametric inequality):

$$|x + y|_p \leq \max(|x|_p, |y|_p) \quad \text{for all } x, y \in \mathbb{Q}. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Equality holds whenever $|x|_p \neq |y|_p$. This is strictly stronger than the usual triangle inequality and is the source of the ultrametric geometry exploited in this paper.

The ring \mathbf{Z}_p and the p -adic expansion. The p -adic integers \mathbf{Z}_p can be defined equivalently as:

- (i) the completion of \mathbf{Z} with respect to $|\cdot|_p$;
- (ii) the inverse limit $\mathbf{Z}_p = \varprojlim_k \mathbf{Z}/p^k\mathbf{Z}$;
- (iii) the set of all sequences (a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots) with each $a_i \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$, written formally as

$$x = a_0 + a_1 p + a_2 p^2 + a_3 p^3 + \dots = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} a_i p^i,$$

with addition and multiplication carried out by carry propagation (exactly as in ordinary base- p arithmetic, but with infinitely many digits to the *left*).

The third viewpoint is the most concrete and is the one used throughout this paper: each p -adic integer is an infinite string of digits $a_0 a_1 a_2 \dots$ from the alphabet $\{0, \dots, p-1\}$, read from least significant digit to most significant. For instance, in \mathbf{Z}_3 the element $x = 2 + 0 \cdot 3 + 1 \cdot 9 + 2 \cdot 27 + \dots$ has digit string $(2, 0, 1, 2, \dots)$. The ring \mathbf{Z}_p is an integral domain, and its fraction field is \mathbf{Q}_p , the field of p -adic numbers. As a metric space under $|\cdot|_p$, the set \mathbf{Z}_p coincides with the closed unit ball $\{x \in \mathbf{Q}_p : |x|_p \leq 1\}$.

Balls in the ultrametric world. For $a \in \mathbf{Z}_p$ and $n \geq 0$, the *ball of radius p^{-n} centered at a* is

$$B(a, p^{-n}) = \{x \in \mathbf{Z}_p : |x - a|_p \leq p^{-n}\} = a + p^n \mathbf{Z}_p.$$

The ultrametric inequality (A.1) forces several properties that have no Euclidean analogue and that are essential to the hierarchical structure of this paper:

- (a) *Every point of a ball is its center.* If $b \in B(a, r)$ then $B(b, r) = B(a, r)$. There is no distinguished “middle”; the ball is defined solely by the radius and any of its elements.
- (b) *Two balls are either disjoint or nested.* If $B(a, r) \cap B(b, s) \neq \emptyset$ and $r \leq s$, then $B(a, r) \subseteq B(b, s)$. Partial overlap never occurs.
- (c) *Every ball is clopen* (simultaneously open and closed). The “sphere” $\{x : |x - a|_p = r\}$ is also open, so it is a clopen set disjoint from the interior; there is no boundary in the topological sense.
- (d) *All triangles are isosceles.* Among any three points, the two largest pairwise distances must be equal: if $|x - z|_p > |x - y|_p$, then $|y - z|_p = |x - z|_p$.

Properties (a)–(b) make balls into a *tree*: the collection of all balls in \mathbf{Z}_p , ordered by reverse inclusion, is a rooted p -ary tree: every ball of radius p^{-n} splits into exactly p disjoint subballs of radius $p^{-(n+1)}$, and no two balls at the same level overlap. This is precisely the rooted prefix tree of Section 3.

Hierarchy and the p -adic expansion. The expansion $x = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} a_i p^i$ encodes this hierarchy digit by digit: the first n digits (a_0, \dots, a_{n-1}) determine which ball of radius p^{-n} contains x , and appending the next digit a_n selects one of its p subballs. Knowing more digits means descending deeper into the tree; two p -adic integers are close precisely when they share a long initial segment. This is the sense in which the p -adic metric is *intrinsically hierarchical*: distance records the depth at which two branches diverge rather than a spatial separation.

Figure A.9: Two ways to visualize \mathbf{Z}_p : a rooted 3-ary tree, a Sierpiński-type planar rendering for $p = 3$, and analogous schematic renderings for $p = 5$ and $p = 7$. Since \mathbf{Z}_p is totally disconnected, these pictures are heuristic visualizations rather than isometric embeddings.

Topological properties. The space $(\mathbf{Z}_p, |\cdot|_p)$ is:

- (i) *compact*: every sequence in \mathbf{Z}_p has a convergent subsequence (equivalently, $\mathbf{Z}_p = \varprojlim \mathbf{Z}/p^k\mathbf{Z}$ is a profinite group);
- (ii) *totally disconnected*: the connected components are singletons; every open set is a union of clopen balls (Figure A.9);
- (iii) *metrizable and perfect*: complete, with no isolated points; topologically homeomorphic to the Cantor set.

These properties underpin the compactness and perfection results of Section 5.

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